

Light Pollution: Laws and Regulations in Serbia and Neighboring Countries

Tamara Blagojević¹

DOI:

Abstract: Light pollution is a growing environmental, health, and astronomical problem. This presentation deals with the legal aspects of light pollution in Serbia, Balkans, EU and neighboring countries, with special reference to the protection of the night sky. To understand the problem, the basic concept and problem of "dark sky protection", as well as related components, will first be briefly explained, including emissions from Earth (street lighting, advertising) and emissions from space (satellites and constellations). Also, potential legal approaches to the problem will be outlined - Environmental Law approach and Space Law approach. Then, an analysis of the existing legal framework in Serbia will be presented in order to understand the current situation and identify legal gaps. In order to identify legal models that could improve domestic regulation, some examples of from neighboring countries, such as Croatia, Slovenia, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic, will also be presented. Additionally, some examples from developed countries with space programmes will be outlined. Finally, based on this comparative review, specific recommendations will be proposed: the inclusion of light pollution and emissions as environmental pollution, regulation amendments to define more precise emission limits and protective measures, harmonization of framework, general and special laws related to environmental protection, and harmonization with, and implementation of, international and regional guidelines and standards for the protection of the dark sky. This approach contributes to a better understanding of the relationship between law, astronomy and environmental protection, and provides a pathway for the strategic development of light pollution law and policy, as well as, lays the foundations for the protection of astronomy and the peaceful use of space in Serbia.

Keywords: light pollution; dark and quiet sky protection; legal framework; environmental law; astronomy / astronomical observation; space law.

Corresponding Author: zvezdana.consult@gmail.com

¹Director of Partnerships at the Space Court Foundation; Business Development Manager at Space Watch.Global; Advisor at Space Career Academy; Member at the International Astronomical Union Centre for Dark and Quiet Skies Protection